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RETHINKING VIRTUAL GALLERIES: CASE STUDIES OF WORKFLOWS IN ART AND RESEARCH PROJECTS

Introduction

According to Oliver Grau, although the history of virtual art has roots extending back to antiquity, it was only with the advancement of digital technology in the 1960s and especially the 1990s that its contemporary development became viable (Grau 2003). These technological changes introduced new requirements for the presentation of artworks, which gradually began to inhabit the digital environment. Successive phases of virtual exhibition development have primarily relied on technologies enabling increasingly immersive, computer-based explorations. Reconstructions of early computer art exhibitions, along with museology and heritage preservation projects such as the Alt-Segeberger Bürgerhaus, illustrate this shift (Kersten et al. 2017).

Through such innovations, visitors gained the ability to engage in interactive tours, access extensive information, and immerse themselves in three-dimensional realities via systems like the HTC Vive. These new virtual spaces enabled the presentation of works created specifically for digital media, which ultimately led to the emergence of the first online museums (Rodrigues, Crippa et al. 2010). In retrospect, virtual galleries can be viewed as new incarnations of traditional exhibition methods, introducing art into cultural and educational life in new and evolving ways (Hendricks, Tangkuampien, and Malan 2003; Ramaiah 2014).

The acceleration of this development was driven by the growing need to move activities online, particularly in response to global challenges (Correia 2018; Giannini and Bowen 2019; Borgdorff, Peters, and Pinch 2020). In today's digital landscape, shaped by the COVID-19 pandemic, approaches to the implementation and dissemination of art and humanities research

have undergone significant transformation. The relocation of numerous activities to virtual spaces has become not only an adaptive strategy but also a new norm, effectively altering the way academic work is conducted. This trend has resulted in a growing corpus of literature on virtual exhibition formats, design tools, and audience engagement (see e.g. Carrozzino et al. 2008; Graham and Cook 2010; Giannini and Bowen 2019; Parisi 2012; Geroimenko 2014; Parsons 2023).

Yet two key questions remain. First, how can virtual galleries serve as effective platforms for integrating artistic and research workflows within the context of the digital humanities? Second, how might we rethink the very notion of the virtual gallery—not only as a curatorial tool but also as an epistemic and technological construct—in light of evolving interdisciplinary practices?

While previous studies have examined virtual exhibitions from curatorial or technological perspectives, fewer have focused on how structured workflows support interdisciplinary collaboration in small-scale, practice-based gallery settings. The lack of attention to such processes is especially evident in discussions of project-based experimentation within independent or hybrid institutions. To address this gap, the article draws on a single-case study of the 3D Blue Point Art Gallery (BPA). Using a range of freely available digital tools, BPA seeks to redefine the relationship between artistic and academic practice in alignment with the principles of digital humanities, artistic research, and open science. Researchers working with BPA—drawing on experience from international projects such as Technologies of Imaging in Communication, Art, and Social Sciences (TICASS) and Communities and Artistic Participation in Hybrid Environments (CAPHE)—are keenly aware of the challenges involved in integrating creative and scholarly activity in interdisciplinary settings. Communication barriers, particularly those arising from methodological and linguistic differences between disciplines, are a recurring issue. Artistic methods, often understood by their creators as forms of inquiry, can be difficult to reconcile with the formal expectations of academic discourse.

From a methodological perspective, the article draws on the case study approach (Yin 2018) and the reflective tradition in artistic research (Candy and Edmonds 2011). It aligns with a practice-based research model in which creative, curatorial, and scholarly activities are embedded within academic inquiry. Rather than abstracting the process into a general framework, we examine selected BPA projects to show how clearly defined workflows structure and shape artistic,

curatorial, and research practices in virtual gallery environments. In doing so, the article investigates how these workflows function as epistemic frameworks—reflecting institutional and technical constraints, while also mediating the complex dialogue between creative and scholarly practices. This approach resonates with broader methodological reflections on practice as research, which foreground the productive tension between tacit, embodied knowledge and formalised academic modes of inquiry (Nelson 2013; Borgdorff 2012). Workflows in this context do not merely facilitate output but constitute knowledge-generating processes in themselves, supporting what Cramer (2021) terms post-digital epistemologies, where creative practice engages critically with technological systems.

The article presents BPA as a micro-laboratory for exploring broader dynamics in digital curation and the integration of artistic and research practices. Rather than comparing multiple institutions, it focuses on a series of internally diverse projects developed within a single gallery. This concentrated lens enables a nuanced, practice-based analysis of how structured workflows emerge and evolve over time. The discussion concludes with a reflection on how such processes can support born-digital collections and collaborative archiving. Virtual galleries are positioned both as experimental arenas for interdisciplinary collaboration and as sustainable infrastructures for preserving digital heritage and expanding access to art and knowledge. A more detailed examination of the featured workflows is provided in the final section, where their methodological, institutional, and conceptual relevance is addressed.

BPA's Project Strategy and the State of the Art in Virtual Exhibition Technologies

To contextualise the following case studies, this section outlines BPA's project strategy within the broader landscape of new media in exhibition design. The London university-affiliated gallery—originally launched at the Polish University Abroad (PUNO) as a response to the pandemic restrictions triggered by COVID-19—emerged from a need to explore and adapt digital tools for creating virtual exhibitions (Solecki 2021).

While not all solutions have withstood the test of time, many initiatives paved the way for virtual exhibitions with realistic 3D space renderings (e.g., Kunstmatrix, Artsteps, Artland). Others, such as collaborative virtual platforms (Spatial) and metaverses (Decentraland, Somnium Space, Cryptovoxels), have offered advanced alternatives for collaborative participation in the

exhibition process, establishing environments that support the formation of remote teams capable of real-time communication. These technologies have introduced unprecedented perspectives, enabling more interactive, personalised, and diverse experiences within virtual spaces (Williams 2022). A pivotal role in crafting dynamic narratives—allowing for the addition of clickable tags, links, and multimedia content to images, videos, and 360-degree materials—has been played by ThingLink. This tool has found broad applications in education, marketing, journalism, and virtual tours, providing contextual information and integrating various content types into cohesive presentations. On the other hand, Mozilla Hubs, with its emphasis on accessibility, privacy, and ease of use, allows for the creation and participation in virtual meetings directly through a browser, without requiring specialised equipment or software (Hubs 2024).

In building advanced, interactive 3D spaces that can be customised for artistic content, Unreal Engine and Unity stand out. Unreal Engine offers exceptional graphic quality and is frequently used in film and television production, where advanced visual effects are essential. Unity, on the other hand, is more versatile and user-friendly, with applications across a wide range of projects, including augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR).

These platforms differ in the programming languages and features they support, which affects content presentation. Unreal Engine uses C++ (Alex 2024), providing sophisticated visual effects but requiring more technical expertise. In contrast, Unity uses C# (Microsoft 2024), making it easier to create interactive, browser-accessible projects. The financial models of these platforms also vary. Kunstmatrix, Spatial and Unity operate on a subscription basis, offering some free tools but charging for advanced features.

Blockchain-based metaverses, like Decentraland and Cryptovoxels, use virtual property trading, enabling users to create customised spaces, such as galleries. Unreal Engine adopts a revenue-sharing model, with fees dependent on the sales revenue generated by applications built on their platform. Creating virtual exhibition spaces also allows for modifications through coding. For instance, Kunstmatrix, built on the Babylon.js library (JavaScript), enables straightforward organisation of virtual exhibitions within a browser. However, it lacks the ability to define custom physics or support advanced interactions.

An alternative to Babylon.js is the widely adopted Three.js library, which simplifies the creation and display of animated 3D graphics in web browsers using WebGL (Parisi 2012). Designed to bridge the gap between complex WebGL programming and accessible 3D content

creation, Three.js has become a cornerstone for developers, designers, and artists aiming to bring immersive 3D experiences to the web. Three.js features a clear structure, is fully JavaScript-based, open source, and independent of commercial projects. It also boasts a developer community nearly four times larger than that of Babylon.js, which contributes to its extensive ecosystem (Dirksen 2023). The library supports integration with frameworks for animations, physics, and virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) tools, making it a versatile choice for creating interactive experiences. Additionally, several popular libraries have been developed based on Three.js, further expanding its capabilities and enabling more complex and dynamic virtual environments. One noteworthy example is React Three Fiber. Developed and released as an open-source project, React Three Fiber is a React "renderer" for Three.js. Rather than a standalone library like Three.js, it acts as a "wrapper" or "binding," providing a declarative approach to building 3D scenes with Three.js using React's component-based architecture.

Recent AI-powered tools—such as GitHub Copilot, Codeium, and GPT-based code assistants—are increasingly used to support development in virtual gallery environments. These tools generate context-aware code, assist with unfamiliar libraries or APIs, and accelerate development workflows. Community-based assistants, such as the Three.js Mentor, further expand learning opportunities, especially for interdisciplinary teams working on complex or unfamiliar systems.

With an awareness of the continuous advancement of modern technologies, BPA has strived to implement practical, sustainable solutions for presenting art and research within the framework of open science. To achieve this, the gallery follows a technology-driven approach grounded in structured processes. These workflows integrate digital tools—such as WebGL, JavaScript, HTML, CSS, and the glTF format—to streamline the creation, documentation, and dissemination of interdisciplinary projects. BPA uses web-accessible 3D graphics to ensure broad audience engagement without the need for specialised software. Interaction is supported through platforms such as Zoom, while exhibition outputs are preserved as open-access publications via repositories like Zenodo (Solecki 2021).

Projects are hosted in decentralised environments to ensure long-term access, archival stability, and resilience against institutional or political shifts (Vukolov 2020). This infrastructure aligns with BPA's broader mission: to bridge curatorial, artistic, and research practices in a sustainable digital ecosystem. It also facilitates experimentation with emerging technologies such

as blockchain-based archiving and the creation of Non-Fungible Tokens (Rabaa'i, Zhu and Jayaraman 2022), allowing BPA to participate in evolving Web3 networks.

To understand how these projects unfold in practice, it is essential to explore the workflows that sustain them. Far from being mere procedural sequences, these structures function as epistemic instruments—shaping the interplay between curatorial vision, technological affordances, and scholarly inquiry. At BPA, projects typically fall into three categories: Art Projects, Research-Exhibition Projects, and Art-Research-Exhibition Projects. The following part of the article outlines representative workflows for each type, illustrating how structured methods enable hybrid practices across artistic creation, curatorial experimentation, and academic research. This perspective explicitly challenges the tool-centric logic that continues to shape much of digital humanities—where technological efficiency often overshadows creative experimentation and collaborative meaning-making (Drucker 2013). Artistic practice, by contrast, seldom treats tools as ends in themselves. It privileges imaginative thinking, symbolic depth, and the cultivation of communicative-artistic communities. Within BPA, workflows operate as mediating structures that facilitate interpretive, affective, and interdisciplinary engagement across diverse media and participants.

Highlighting these processes brings to light alternative modes of knowledge production frequently overlooked in technocentric research paradigms. It underscores the essential role of the arts in digital culture—not as ornamental extensions of technical infrastructures, but as catalysts of critical invention and epistemic diversity (Svensson 2016). Seen in this way, curatorial and artistic practices do not stand apart from technological innovation, but enter into productive dialogue with it—generating situated, repeatable, and diversified approaches that enrich the methodological landscape of the digital humanities.

BPA's Standard Workflow for Art Projects

The workflow for these types of projects begins with conceptualisation and collaborative planning. At this stage, objectives, themes, and a timeline are developed jointly by artists, curators, and external partners. This is followed by the creation of digital content tailored to each exhibition, accompanied by curatorial texts. These materials are then integrated into bespoke virtual environments designed to support the specific character of each project.

Figure 1. Diagram of BPA's workflow for art projects by Justyna Gorzkowicz: A visual representation of the key phases involved in conceptualizing, developing, and presenting artistic projects within the virtual gallery framework.

A core feature of BPA's model is its adaptive virtual space. The gallery does not function as a static exhibition container but transforms in response to each project's conceptual logic. It may become part of the artistic installation itself—as in *The Dystopia of an Imitation* by Jarosław Solecki—or serve as a curated environment for presenting digital artworks from external initiatives, as seen in *Wake-Up Call* (Virtual Biennale Prague, 2020).

In *Dystopia of an Imitation* (Arts Council England, 2021–2023), Solecki combined traditional sculpture with generative augmented reality (AR) elements, resulting in a hybrid artwork inspired by Vermeer's *Milkmaid* (Solecki 2023b). Developed within BPA's virtual infrastructure, this research-based installation progressed to public exhibitions and scholarly dissemination in a hybrid format. A vital stage in the workflow—particularly in opening up artistic research to wider audiences—is dissemination.

Figure 2. *Photographic documentation by Jaroslaw Solecki: Development of the hybrid project from Dystopia of Imitation to The Milkmaid's Pitcher.*

Projects are promoted through targeted outreach strategies and supported by supplementary events such as curator-led tours, artist talks, or e-book launches. The final phase is evaluation, aligned with the public release and archival documentation of the exhibition. Feedback from both creators and audiences informs future practice and improves the long-term quality of BPA's open-access materials.

As illustrated in the diagram (fig. 1), three phases stand out as particularly resource-intensive: content development, virtual exhibition creation, and archiving. These stages define the collaborative and technical backbone of BPA's approach to art-centred digital projects.

BPA's Standard Workflow for Research-Exhibition Projects

The workflow used in this category of BPA initiatives diverges from the model applied in standard art projects. It introduces an additional core module: research integration. Together with content development, this phase defines the academic scope of the initiative and requires significant coordination. Another distinguishing aspect is the emphasis on side events, which often take on hybrid or performative formats and demand the most time and resources. While the virtual exhibition remains an important outcome, it is embedded within a broader, multi-stage process that concludes with post-exhibition activities and long-term archiving.

Figure 3. BPA workflow for research–exhibition projects by Justyna Gorzkowicz. Diagram of phases and activities involved in planning, producing, and presenting research-based exhibitions, including virtual and post-show elements.

As with art projects, the process begins with conceptualisation and planning, where exhibition goals are shaped in dialogue with academic frameworks and curatorial aims. In this category, however, the emphasis shifts: exhibitions may present digitised archival materials,

ethnographic collections, or other cultural artefacts aligned with specific research agendas. The content does not need to be strictly artistic but often emerges from interdisciplinary inquiry.

A representative example is *Vincenz's Dialogues – Views* (2023–2024), created within the scope of the international project *Exploring the Works of Stanisław Vincenz in the 21st Century – an Interdisciplinary Approach* (2021–2024), involving partners from the UK, Poland, Ukraine, and Israel. The exhibition incorporated ethnographic documentation—especially rare photographs of the Hutsul region by Lidia Cipriani (1933)—and was accompanied by regional music. The BPA gallery space was morphically adapted to accommodate the narrative, allowing the exhibition to unfold as a performative and immersive event.

Figure 4. Expanded exhibition room in *Vincenz's Dialogues – Views*. Photo by Jarosław Solecki.

Post-exhibition activities in this workflow include the creation of print and digital publications, audiovisual documentation, and dissemination through scholarly and public channels. These outputs extend the life of the project, ensuring its contribution to academic discourse and broader cultural engagement.

BPA's Standard Workflow for Art-Research-Exhibition Project

This type of hybrid initiative at BPA follows a structure similar to the research-exhibition model, though with distinct emphases. As shown in the workflow diagram, preparing the exhibition stands on equal footing with the development of side events—both treated as core components of the project. In this context, the exhibition moves beyond digital humanities frameworks and is repositioned within an art-led inquiry. The initial phases, such as “conceptualisation and planning” and “art and research integration,” involve the collaborative formulation of thematic and methodological questions. Interdisciplinary partnerships between artists and scholars are fundamental at this stage.

Figure 5. BPA workflow for art–research–exhibition projects by Justyna Gorzkowicz. Diagram showing integrated processes combining artistic, research, and exhibition elements, including concept development, research, side events, and follow-up.

An example illustrating this workflow in practice is the BPA project *The Question of ‘Identity’ in an Interdisciplinary Approach* (2020–2021). Co-organised by BPA, PUNO, and the Faculty of Art at the Pedagogical University of Kraków, the project centred on the theme of

identity. Originating in the visual arts, the initiative invited collaboration and created a platform for scholars in the humanities and social sciences to present their perspectives during an international, interdisciplinary conference. The resulting exhibition became a space where artistic and academic insights converged—producing new narratives and modes of interpretation (Images of Identity 2020).

Figure 6. Visual overview of the Three.js editing interface and internal exhibition spaces from Images of Identity. Photo by Jarosław Solecki.

Exhibit Execution Workflow: Implementation in BPA Projects

What unites all BPA projects is, without a doubt, the implementation of exhibitions in an interactive gallery environment. This stage also has its own advanced workflow, which warrants discussion here. Importantly, the gallery does not have a fixed design—it is flexible and shaped to fit the needs of each individual project.

Figure 7. Exhibit execution workflow by Justyna Gorzkowicz: Diagram illustrating the key stages of the virtual exhibition production process, from digitising objects to dynamic loading within a WebGL environment.

In every case, the exhibition environment is developed closely with the curators to reflect the specific goals of the project. For instance, the exhibition of 19th-century sketches by Cyprian Norwid was presented in a single virtual room, where colour was used to create an intimate setting. In contrast, the *Images of Identity* group exhibition and Lidio Cipriani's ethnographic showcase used multiple connected rooms, each designed to reflect different perspectives. In Jarosław Solecki's solo show, the BPA gallery became part of the artwork itself, forming a dynamic and co-created virtual installation.

This level of gallery interactivity enhances visitor engagement and deepens the experience of virtual exhibitions. The flexibility in designing BPA's virtual spaces supports a wide range of artistic and research aims. Such adaptability also expands the potential for creative interpretation and expression, which merits further exploration in future studies.

Figure 8. Room model in Blender: Texture baking process as part of virtual exhibition preparation. Photo by Jaroslaw Solecki.

Figure 9. General view from Blender showing the expanded exhibition spaces of BPA projects. Designed by Jaroslaw Solecki

The technical implementation of exhibitions usually begins with digitising objects—whether 2D images or 3D sculptures—into high-resolution bitmap files. A curated selection is then processed further. This approach was used in *Dystopia of Imitation*, where real objects were 3D-scanned and transformed into a virtual artwork within a hybrid installation. In other cases, digital artworks are submitted directly, with raw bitmap files refined in subsequent processing.

At this stage, Adobe Photoshop is commonly used to adjust visual parameters such as colour balance and contrast. In the *Wake-Up Call* project, particular care was taken to ensure consistency in the black and white tones of the posters, reinforcing their monochrome aesthetic in the virtual setting. With its AI-powered tools, Photoshop also supports the restoration and enhancement of visual material—especially valuable when working with historical documents.

Figure 10. Developer tools in the web browser showing the process of optimising code and textures in preparation for the exhibition. Part of the BPA projects. Optimisation of textures and other elements for virtual display. Photo by Jaroslaw Solecki.

The next stage involves compressing image and texture files into the .ktx2 format, which improves rendering efficiency through mipmap generation and the inclusion of embedded metadata. In *Dystopia of Imitation*, this optimisation was essential for ensuring fluid performance,

particularly when handling complex or layered visual elements. For static scenes, lighting is carefully mapped to enhance atmosphere while maintaining performance. In dynamic installations such as *Dystopia of Imitation* and *Vincenz Dialogues – Views*, lighting is applied selectively and locally, creating mood and spatial depth without increasing loading times. In certain BPA projects, sound is also integrated at this stage, with attention paid to optimising audio quality relative to file size.

3D modelling in Blender enables the creation of detailed, high-resolution virtual objects that align with curatorial and artistic goals. These are rendered in WebGL environments using dynamically loaded resources, which improve memory management on the viewer's device. This layered optimisation process enriches the virtual exhibition experience and enhances audience engagement through smoother, more immersive interaction.

Discussion

As demonstrated by the case studies, BPA treats the virtual gallery not as a static display container but as a responsive, evolving environment shaped by the needs of each project. Its spatial form is not fixed—it transforms according to the conceptual framework, visual language, and curatorial approach of individual exhibitions. In this way, the gallery becomes an active part of the creative process, adapting to emerging ideas and facilitating collaboration between artists, researchers, and audiences.

This flexible approach is supported by structured digital workflows, which serve not only as organisational tools but also as frameworks for knowledge-making. These workflows help translate artistic and curatorial ideas into programmable environments, connecting creative thinking with digital methods. While BPA draws on technological innovation, it does not reduce the process to tool usage alone. Instead, it foregrounds the interpretive and imaginative role of the arts in digital humanities, advocating for models that leave room for experimentation and cultural sensitivity (cf. Giannini and Bowen 2019; Hackbart-Dean et al. 2023).

However, building and sustaining this kind of digital practice presents clear challenges. Developing interactive 3D content requires advanced technical skills and constant learning. Software such as Blender and WebGL demands time, effort, and financial resources that may exceed the capacity of smaller institutions (Graham and Cook 2010). The rapid pace of

technological change also makes it difficult to keep up with new platforms and tools (Parsons 2023). Additionally, digital exclusion remains a significant issue, as not all users have access to high-speed internet or compatible devices (Bartscherer and Coover 2011).

To address these issues, BPA prioritises low-barrier access. Projects are designed to run in browsers without requiring specialised equipment or software. Mobile-friendly layouts, lightweight animations, and scalable interfaces help make exhibitions accessible across devices and contexts. In parallel, decentralised storage solutions—such as IPFS—are employed to ensure long-term availability and integrity of cultural content (Vukolov 2020).

BPA’s model also emphasises ecological awareness. Recognising the environmental impact of high-energy 3D rendering, the gallery adopts techniques such as file compression and optimised animation to reduce energy use (Williams 2022). The goal is to maintain quality while lowering the carbon footprint of digital practice.

Figure 11. Dystopia of Imitation NFTs featured on OpenSea. Photo by Jaroslaw Solecki, highlighting 3D model works generated in the project.

In addition, BPA explores the potential of decentralised technologies to rethink ownership, preservation, and funding models. For example, in *The Milkmaid's Pitcher*, NFTs were used to certify and distribute selected digital artefacts. These tokens not only ensured authenticity but also introduced new forms of limited-edition fundraising and collector engagement. Such strategies reflect a broader interest in Web3-based infrastructure and its possibilities for peer-to-peer circulation of art and knowledge

Complementing this, BPA is developing a decentralised, publicly accessible archive to store exhibition assets and research materials. This platform is designed to increase transparency, data sovereignty, and long-term access—particularly for small cultural institutions with limited server capacity. These initiatives align with BPA's commitment to experimental, socially engaged scholarship, and offer a framework for cultural institutions navigating digital transformation.

Figure 12. BPA Archive project: Multiple views displaying the expanded sidebar menu, with an environment map and references to supplementary information. Photo by Jaroslaw Solecki.

Taken together, these strategies reflect a model of digital practice grounded in accessibility, interdisciplinarity, and long-term resilience. BPA embraces its potential as a co-creative medium—one that expands the space for dialogue between art, research, and technological experimentation.

Conclusion

BPA's experience demonstrates that 3D galleries need not be seen as lesser counterparts to physical exhibitions. On the contrary, they can operate as dynamic spaces for research, creativity, and collaboration—environments where ideas emerge and technology plays a facilitative rather than dominant role. Far from being mere platforms for display, these online exhibition spaces participate actively in processes of meaning-making. Positioned between artistic experimentation and curatorial practice, the virtual gallery takes shape as a co-producer of knowledge within the evolving domains of digital art and the humanities. BPA's model illustrates how such platforms can merge creative and academic workflows, reframing the gallery as an epistemic environment—one that generates understanding through iterative design, conceptual structure, and methodological clarity.

BPA avoids reliance on any single technological solution. Instead, it uses reproducible workflows supported by open repositories and collaboratively developed design protocols. Within this framework, insight emerges from curatorial choices, spatial composition, and the crafting of digital artefacts. The focus shifts away from dependency on specific tools toward a mode of inquiry shaped by processes, not platforms. In this setting, technology acts not as a focal point but as an instrument for dialogue, interdisciplinarity, and reflective engagement. BPA thus presents an alternative to engineering-driven models in digital creative practice—an ethos rooted in openness, adaptability, and co-production. This perspective calls for a deeper re-evaluation of the ways in which digital infrastructures influence both artistic and scholarly practices.

Although grounded in Polish literary and cultural traditions, BPA's initiatives resonate across linguistic and disciplinary boundaries. Through multilingual access, open-source frameworks, and cross-border partnerships, the gallery contributes to broader debates on cultural preservation, public knowledge-sharing, and interdisciplinary inquiry. It counters the notion of virtual exhibitions as static content holders, proposing instead that they function as active agents in the creation, mediation, and transformation of meaning.

In response to the guiding questions: online galleries can serve as effective frameworks for integrating creative and research-based processes when grounded in transparency, reflection, and methodical design—where curatorial work, spatial logic, and digital experimentation converge. More broadly, we may reconceptualise the virtual gallery not only as a tool for curation, but as a

hybrid epistemic and technological construct—capable of producing insight, supporting experimentation, and bridging disciplinary divides within the continually evolving field of the digital humanities.

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